

Harmony of National and Universal Values in Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT

This article studies the process of improving the relationship between national and universal values in the development of a democratic society, the socio-philosophical analysis of the role of SDGs and priorities and principles of the strategy of spiritual renewal. Moreover, article clarifies the process of transformation national and universal values and its influence to the uprising of Uzbek cultural heritage.

Keywords: Cultural renewal; Tolerance; Progress; Justice; Enlightenment; SDGs; Reforms; Festival; Values; Cultural heritage.

Introduction

Cultural renewal is a process in which the cultural life of a society is connected with change, development and enrichment. Events occurring in the life of people and society bring about certain changes in the consciousness and culturality of the individual. If culturality is not renewed and enriched, the development of society can be interrupted and hindered to progress. Changes in the development of society, in the era of new reforms, there are also serious changes in culturality, and at the same time impacting the culturality on the processes taking place in society. In such processes, the levels of cultural renewal are also accelerated. For example, the adoption of the Strategy of Actions in Uzbekistan has given a great impetus to the revival of national cultural values in the country, the organization of various festivals and the presentation of the national culturality and culture of Uzbekistan to the world community. Particular attention to the processes of cultural renewal in Uzbekistan has had a significant impact on the change of people's consciousness, lifestyle, and community events in society. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev underlines the following: "For us, work in the field of culturality and enlightenment is inextricably linked with patriotic education and is a matter of honor. One who has high moral qualities always lives with love for the Motherland. After all, such vivid human qualities are primarily manifested in selfless service to their country and people" [1].

Methods

In the preparation of the article, methods of scientific knowledge such as analysis and synthesis, retrospective, comparative analysis, generalization, dialectical and synergetic have been used.

Main Part

Today, Uzbekistan is developing its own unique system and experience in the further development of cultural life. Consequently, the tasks outlined in the Strategy of Action for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 have been implemented into life, programs such as "Obod qishloq", "Obod mahalla", "Youth - our future" as well as "Five important initiatives", "The Concept of Development of National Idea in a

New Stage of Development of Uzbekistan”, “Concept of Continuous Cultural Education” are of great importance for new thinking and working of the population. As a result of this, the scope of these reforms has been extended even to the most remote regions of Uzbekistan, and serves both to radically renew the architectural appearance of the regions and to improve the well-being of the people.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev “On measures to develop the national idea for a new stage of development of Uzbekistan” dated April 8, 2019, the development of the project “National idea development at a new stage of development of Uzbekistan” has launched a new stage in the cultural and cultural life of the country. In this concept, not only the national experience of the Uzbek people has been applied, but also the advanced experience of the democratically developed countries of the world has been studied, a number of philosophers, creative intellectuals, experts and leading specialists of research centers of the Republic have been involved in its development.

As a result, the Concept defines the highest priority tasks for which the country will be based on the idea of national development. In the idea of national development, peace, solidarity and tolerance of citizens and nationalities in Uzbekistan, democratic principle, full decision-making, human rights and freedoms, rule of law and justice, material and cultural life development has been expressed. From this point of view, at the present stage of development of Uzbekistan it is determined to go from national revival to the great goal of national development. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev commented on this: “Of paramount importance is the development of the cultural and moral world of our people, especially youth. Therefore, the most crucial task for us is youth education on the basis of the idea “From national revival to national progress”, in the spirit of patriotism, devotion to the Motherland”.

The main ideas of the concept From the national revival to the national development –“The feeling of a single homeland”, “Justice - in the rule of law”, “People’s consent”, “Enlightenment against ignorance”, “Innovative development”. Their main purpose is to enhance all spheres of life of the state and society, to give Uzbek people a sense of creativity and creativity.

It is noteworthy that much attention is being paid to the regular implementation of the socio-economic reforms carried out in the country at the moment, the legislative acts adopted, and the state programs, the propaganda work aimed at bringing the content and essence of national conceptions to the broad strata of the population. In this regard, the importance of the resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev “On additional measures to improve the effectiveness of cultural and educational work” dated May 3, 2019 is incomparable. Based on this Decree, a non-profit non-governmental organization “Ma’rifat” with its legal framework was established at the Republican Center for Culturality and Enlightenment to effectively carry out its propaganda work. It is established that the society is a non-profit non-governmental organization, which is the Republican center of Culturality and enlightenment, and carries out its activities in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Today, groups of propagandists consisting of its territorial departments, prominent specialists of the sphere, cultural and artistic figures and creative intellectuals are formed. In addition, financial and cultural promotion of

propagandists, including payment for their lectures in cultural and Educational Activities, Contest “**Ma’rifat ziyolilari**”, badge “**Ma’naviyat fidoyisi**” were introduced.

Based on the tasks set out in the Strategy Actions for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, attention is paid to increasing the role of cinema in instilling in the minds of Uzbek youth respect for national and universal values, love for the motherland. In our opinion, the recent economic concepts are generally meaningful have a different meaning. The most important of factor for achieving the high levels of human indicator is employment. The human indicators are related with the modern processes of reforms. The concept of human development has not lost its relevance even today, clearly age or not clearly defined by any other criteria. In terms of the number of employees of any enterprise, their number who have the ability and right to work in a broad sense, and on their own the ability of a country to produce any consumption value we can understand the total population.

In addition, there is no doubt that the promotion of cultural heritage and the formation of a sense of respect for it in the hearts of young people will contribute to the rise of the human criterion on the basis of the establishment of the second international status festival in the city of Shahrissabz, the celebration of 145-year-old birthday of enlightened The practical confirmation of these reforms was announced on the basis of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev “On measures to further increase the role and influence of the culture and art sphere in the life of society” dated April 15, 2020 in the country “Day of culture and Art Workers of the Republic of Uzbekistan”.

In addition, the Uzbek National Institute of Musical Arts named after Yunus Rajabi and the Research Institute of Cultural Heritage in the form of a state institution have been established in the country. In particular, the Republican Specialized Music Academic Lyceums named after V.Uspensky and R.Glier were transformed into the Republican Specialized Music Schools named after V.Uspensky and R.Glier, respectively. The reorganization and reestablishment of the State Dance Ensemble “Bahor” named after Mukarrama Turgunbaeva under the Ministry of Culture on the basis of the decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on February 4, 2020 “On measures to further develop the art of national dance” is also an important news in the cultural life of the country.

In short, the greatest wealth of Uzbekistan today is the human factor. At the heart of the large-scale strategic reforms being carried out in the country, the priority is to improve the living standards of the population, to ensure the well-being of each of our compatriots, to create all conditions for their happy life. The pace of strategic reforms in the country is mobilizing this goal to become a reality.

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan to approve the “Concept of continuous cultural education” on December 31, 2019 on the formation of social skills and qualities that are important for the independent life of the younger generation in the Republic, step-by-step, education of young people as a high-quality, harmonious generation was a big step. This concept covers the following four stages as given in chart below. In general, the main goal of this consortium is to increase the knowledge of the Uzbek people on the upbringing of children, their pedagogical culture, to constantly inform citizens about effective methods of continuous cultural education and forms of implementation.

It is worth noting that the results of cultural renewal in Uzbekistan can be seen in the positive changes in the life of the people, in the improvement of human relations in society and in the propaganda work carried out in the field of culturality. In this process, the media, which is operating in Uzbekistan, has a significant impact on the educational system, theater, cinema, art literature, art, philosophy and ethics. They are also the main spheres of cultural renewal in the country. Changes in this sphere have become the priority direction of the development of society in Uzbekistan. These strategic reforms, which serve the cultural renewal of the country in years 2019-2020, can be analyzed through the following areas:

Today, Uzbekistan pays great attention to the development of literature, along with all other spheres and sectors. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev states: “In order to further develop our cultural life, a number of important documents, including decisions and decrees on increasing the culture of reading, improving the sphere of culture and art, the creation of creative schools and centers named after great artists in the regions, were also adopted.

Speaking about this, the construction of the alley of writers in Tashkent City, the establishment of memorial complexes dedicated to the great figures of our literature, as well as the Great Enlightenment in the Namangan region, the lesson domla, Hamid Alimjan, Zulfiya and SharafRashidov, outstanding creators in the city of Jizzakh, singer Komiljon Otaniyozov, people’s poet Ibroyim Yusupov hero of Uzbekistan in Nukus, Fergana, Kashkadarya in the regions Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Oripov, it should be noted that works are being carried out to perpetuate the memories of Muhammad Yusuf’ [2].

The practical confirmation of these ideas, highlighted by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, can be seen in the example of the fact that in 2019 the great encyclopedic scientist Abu Rayhon Beruni published VIII volume consisting of the works “Harakatlanish yo’li”, “Zijlar yog’dusi” and “Cartography”.

The work “Harakatlanishyo’li” is devoted to the fact that the blue lights move in a certain direction in the sky, and the science of the stars. “Zijlar yog’dusi” is an Indian work of Vijay Nandi, an Indian work of “Karan tilak”, related to the science of astronomy.

Beruni filled the text of the translation of this work with other Indian catalog of stars, commenting on them and explaining his thoughts. This masterpiece is useful for professionals, researchers, students, as well as anyone interested in astronomy and cartography knowledge.

One more such news, 2019 year was adopted by UNESCO on the celebration of the 1000th anniversary of the rare work of Ibn Sina “Canon of Medicine”. “Canones of Medicine” is the first in the world scientific approach to the state of a healthy and unhealthy body. The celebration of the 1000 anniversary of this work is considered a symbol of the birth of scientific technology. Undoubtedly, Avicenna made a worthy contribution to the development of the world science with its unique creation, rich cultural heritage, and the international award of UNESCO named after the thinker was also established, which proves that it is universally recognized by the world community.

The Jadid movement’s role in the development of Uzbek national literature is invaluable. With the efforts of the jadids, the Uzbek press, novels and dramaturgy came into being. Currently, the works created by them are translated to foreign languages and presented to foreign readers. Recently, on the occasion of the 125th anniversary of the birth of Abdulla Kadiri, one of the great figures of jadid literature, the novel “O’tkan kunlar” of the great writer was translated and published in English by British literary critics and American Translators.

For the first time the novel was translated into English by Mark Edward Riz, an American translator and researcher from the Uzbek language, and was published in the US under the name “Bygone days”. It is also worth noting that it is included in the catalog of the largest library in the United States – the library of Congress. Also, the publication of this work in the form of e-book will undoubtedly help Uzbek literature take its place among the world literature.

The second English-language version of the novel was authored by British literary critic Carol Yermakova and published in France’s famous Nouveau Monde Editions under the name “Days gone by” sponsored by the Islam Karimov Foundation.

Currently, the translation of such masterpieces in Uzbek into foreign languages, in particular English, French, Korean, Russian, Chinese and other languages, promotes the recognition of Uzbek literature in the world community. These days, the most popular Uzbek works such as “Yulduzli tunlar”, “Humoyun va Akbar”, “Dunyoning ishlari”, “Shum bola”, “O’tmishdan ertaklar” have also been translated into foreign languages and are on the eve of publication.

In February 2020, the Islamic Heritage Foundation of Great Britain “Al-Furqan” presented to the Imam Bukhari International Research Center about a hundred unique Arabic, Turkish and Persian manuscripts, catalogs stored in World funds. It is noted that, it provides an opportunity to obtain valuable information about the works stored in libraries and manual funds in these lands through a series of rare manuscripts, catalogues published in African countries such as Burkina Faso, Cote d’Ivoire, as well as in a number of European countries. As a result, it provides an opportunity for Uzbek scholars to study and explore the scientific and cultural heritage of their great ancestors.

On the occasion of the 579th anniversary of the birth of Alisher Navoi, the prose of the great figure “Khamsa” in the prose of the poem “Farhad and Shirin” was first published in English by poet and translator Azam Obidov and presented to English readers. As an example of one of the cultural updates in Uzbek national literature, in November 2019, the novel “Night and Day” (“Kechavakunduz”) by Abdulhamid Suleiman oglu Chulpan, one of

the founders of Uzbek poetry and literature, was translated into English by Christopher Fort, a lecturer of the Department of Slavic languages and literature of the University of Michigan, USA. On January 17, 2020 the Embassy of Uzbekistan in London hosted a presentation of the work. On January 17 this year; the Embassy of Uzbekistan in London hosted a presentation of the work. In general, this novel is one of the important steps to the world recognition of Uzbek literature.

The dialectical connection of nationality and universality is manifested in the expression of the connection between the general aspects of things and events through commonality, and in the determination of its own appearance through individuality. The whole being, nature and society as a whole, as a result of the interaction of commonality and privateness, simultaneously manifests itself as a common and continuous phenomenon, causing both national and universal interconnection, complementing and reflecting each other.

There are both national and universal aspects in the social realities of humanity, such as morality, art, culture and religion, and their interdependence shows the balance of nationality and universality. The ratio of nationality and universality in cultural renewal, therefore, depends on the degree to which these aspects are intertwined in phenomena such as its integral parts, morality, art, politics, and ideology.

Therefore, we consider it necessary to pay attention to the following factors in the issue of the national and universal dialectic of the peoples of the world:

First, enriching the national culture, history, language, national values, recognizing the harmony of universal culture, values and cultures, raising them from the national revival to a new stage and increasing their effectiveness, raising the awareness of national identity and ensuring cultural renewal of society;

Second, the development of the language, culture, values and traditions of all nations and peoples living in the country, the implementation of large-scale reforms in creating the conditions created for them;

Third, to educate the younger generation in the spirit of new and rational thinking, respect for national and universal humanity, which will serve innovative development;

Fourth, to bring up a physically and culturally healthy generation by achieving high results in science, technology, innovation, education and upbringing, culture and arts;

Fifth, the development of all types of intellectual property, the creation of practically all opportunities to demonstrate the intellectual potential of people.

Today, Uzbekistan actively cooperates with international organizations in order to establish intercultural dialogue in the world community, thereby introducing its national culturality and culture to the peoples of the world. In this regard, activities in the field of development of international cultural relations with UNESCO, preservation of universal and national heritage are of particular importance. "To this day, 300 centuries-old masterpieces of 88 countries - customs, traditions, holidays, food, folklore, songs, dances - are included in the list of intangible cultural heritage of humankind." (Table below) [3].

Year of entry	The name of intangible cultural heritages of Uzbekistan
1990	Ichan Fortress of Khiva
1993	Bukhara
2000	Historical center of Shakhrisabz
2001	Samarkand
2008	Shashmaqom
2008	The ancient ethnographic site of Surkhandarya region is the cultural site of Boysun district
2009	Traditional song of Fergana valley – “Katta ashula”
2009	“Palov culture and traditions”
2009	Eastern New Year – Navruz
2014	the humorous art of the Uzbek people - Askiya
2016	Palov
2019	Lazgi
2020	Miniature art
2021	Bakhshi art
2022	Sericulture and traditional production of silk for weaving
2022	Telling tradition of Nasreddin Hodja/ Molla Nesreddin/ Molla Ependi/ Apendi/ Afendi Kozhanasyr Anecdotes

In addition, Uzbekistan’s cultural cooperation with UNESCO is based on the birthdays of great scholars and statesmen such as Imam Bukhari, Ahmad Fergani, Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Kamoliddin Behzod, historical cities such as Bukhara, Khiva, Samarkand, Termez, Shakhrisabz, Karshi, Tashkent, Margilan. We can also see the great literary heritage of our people in the joint celebration of the epic “Alpomish”, the historical written monument “Avesta” and the historical anniversaries of the Khorezm Mamun Academy [4].

Today, UNESCO plays an invaluable role in recognizing the contribution of Uzbekistan’s tangible and intangible heritage to the culture of world civilization.

As a result, in the process of intercultural dialogue, Uzbekistan is gaining a worthy position among the countries of the world. Uzbekistan supports such strategic activities of UNESCO and has ratified many international documents of the organization on the development of bilateral cooperation. In particular, Uzbekistan acceded to the UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity, adopted in November 2001, which promotes the preservation and promotion of cultural diversity around the world. This declaration serves to promote the recognition of cultural

diversity, understanding of human unity and the development of intercultural dialogue. In accordance with this declaration, the principles of universal culture are recognized in Uzbekistan [5].

Conclusion

In summary, in the process of cultural development, nationalism and universality are linked dialectically with each other. That is why nationality and universality are interdependent in the process of strategic development, and it is impossible to separate them from each other or to put them in opposition to each other. This can lead to huge losses in culture, culturality and enlightenment. Therefore, the dialectical connection between universality and nationality is an important factor for cultural renewal in society. Relying on the dialectic of nationality and universality in cultural renewal plays a decisive role in the strategy of democratic development and cultural development.

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this study.

References

- [1] President Shavkat Mirziyoev's speech at the Independence Day central festival event in Tashkent. Xalq so'zi Newspaper, September 1 2019 (No. 180).
- [2] Adabiyot va san'at, madaniyatni rivojlantirish – xalqimiz ma'naviy olamini yuksaltirishning mustahkam poydevoridir. Xalq so'zi gazetasi, 2017.
- [3] Uzbekistan - UNESCO: Cooperation for Peace and Goodness //http://uza.uz/uz/culture/o-zbekiston-yunesko-tinchlik-va-ezgulik-yo-lidagi-hamkorlik-15-11-2016.
- [4] Uzbekistan. <https://whc.unesco.org/en/statesparties/uz>.
- [5] UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity. Records of the General Conference, 31st Session, Paris, 15 October to 3 November 2001, Volume 1: Resolutions – Paris: UNESCO, 2002, Pages 61-66.
- [6] Sobirovich T. B. (2022). National and universal principles of democracy. Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities, 12(1): 334-338.
- [7] Sobirovich T. B. (2021). The implementation of human indicator reforms in Uzbekistan. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, 10(9): 197-202.

[8] Sobirovich T. B. (2021). National Principles of Democracy in Uzbekistan. *Mediterranean Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences (MJBAS)*, 5(3): 131-135.

[9] Sobirovich T. B. (2021). Philosophical Dialectics of National and Universal Cultural Development. *Irish Interdisciplinary Journal of Science & Research*.

[10] Sobirovich T. B. (2020). Strategy of Renewal of National Spirituality of Uzbekistan. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(8): 122-126.